

On finding empirical upper bound models for latency guarantees in packet-optical networks

Nataliia Koneva
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
nkoneva@pa.uc3m.es

Alfonso Sánchez-Macián
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
alfonsan@it.uc3m.es

José Alberto Hernández
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
jahgutie@it.uc3m.es

Farhad Arpanaei
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
farpanae@it.uc3m.es

Óscar González de Dios
Telefonica CTIO
Madrid, Spain
oscar.gonzalezdedios@telefonica.com

Abstract—Accurate estimation of queuing delays is crucial for designing and optimizing communication networks, particularly in the context of Deterministic Networking (DetNet) scenarios. This study investigates the approximation of queuing delays using an M/M/1 envelope model, which provides a simple methodology to find tight upper bounds of real delay percentiles. Real traffic statistics collected at Internet Exchange Points (like Amsterdam and San Francisco) have been used to fit polynomial regression models for transforming packet queuing delays into the M/M/1 envelope models. We finally propose a methodology for providing delay percentiles in DetNet scenarios where tight latency guarantees need to be assured.

Index Terms—Packet-Optical Networks; Queuing models; Latency; Deterministic Networking.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deterministic networking (DetNet) is a new paradigm for network design and management that seeks to ensure predictable and reliable network performance, including bounded latency and reliability [1], [2]. This approach can be useful for applications that require low latency and high throughput, such as real-time communications and industrial automation [3], [4]. However, deterministic networks are often challenging to design and analyze due to the complexity of the queuing behavior of network devices. In particular, queuing delays can be difficult to model and predict accurately, especially when traffic is bursty and the number of independent uncorrelated sources is small [5].

DetNet aims to provision deterministic data paths for real-time applications, ensuring extremely low packet loss rates, low jitter, and bounded end-to-end latency for Quality-of-Service (QoS) assurance. A critical issue in providing deterministic services is allocating the right resources to ensure quality of service (QoS) requirements within a network slice [6].

In this sense, the authors in [1] discussed the necessity for low and controlled latency in 5G networks to support time-sensitive applications. For instance, in cloud gaming, an end-to-end latency of 50 – 80 ms ensures a smooth experience, while 120 ms can significantly impact responsiveness. Also,

other scenarios like telemedicine, robotic surgery, connected vehicles, AR/VR and Industrial IoT demand top connectivity guarantees in terms of packet loss and latency [7]–[9].

In some cases, DetNet segments should have slotted, scheduled, and synchronous architectures to cover these strict performance requirements. This has given rise to defining strategies for Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) which, in combination with DetNet, can provide near-lossless packet forwarding with deterministic latency.

TSN refers to the transmission of packets that must be processed within a specified time frame, usually measured in microseconds. TSN is crucial for applications that require high levels of accuracy and precision, such as robotic systems and autonomous vehicles. For instance, the authors of [2] propose a packet engine that supports 100 Gb/s throughput, assure bounded latency of less than 6.25 μ s per node, and provides lossless packet during network failures, demonstrating its efficacy in maintaining high reliability and performance.

In the past years, network traffic has been revisited and it has been found that traffic volumes approximate the Gaussian distribution [10], [11], and they can be even better characterized by a log-normal distribution, especially in scenarios where high aggregation of multiple independent sources occur [5], [12]. In fact, packet inter-arrival times can be approximated by a non-homogeneous Poisson process, and the M/G/1 queuing model can be applied for characterising packet delays [13]. However, the M/G/1 model does not have a closed-form expression for the cumulative density function (CDF) of queuing delays, thus making the task of computing delay percentiles and worst-case latency values difficult for network modelers.

This work aims to provide a simple queuing delay model that can be used as an upper bound for estimating latency bounds in networking scenarios. To do this, we use non-linear regression, a subset of Machine Learning (ML) techniques for building accurate models from data.

The remainder of this work is organized as follows: Section II briefly reviews classical queuing theory results and the goal of defining an M/M/1 based queuing model that acts as an

upper bound for generic network traffic. Section III shows the accuracy of the M/M/1 envelope model in different network scenarios; its applicability at evaluating delay percentile estimates in different network scenarios is evaluated in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes this article with its main findings and take-away messages.

II. BACKGROUND AND METHODOLOGY

The simplest delay model for network engineers is the well-known M/M/1 queuing model, where packets are assumed to arrive following a Poisson process with rate λ packet/s and packet service times X are exponentially distributed with a mean of μ^{-1} seconds per packet. In M/M/1 models, the CDF of queuing plus transmission delay D per queue follows an exponential distribution:

$$F_D(t) = 1 - e^{-\mu(1-\rho)t}, \quad t \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

where the server's load $\rho = \frac{\lambda}{\mu}$ is the ratio between the packet arrival intensity λ (in packet/s) and the service rate μ (in packet/s). Remark that ρ must be smaller than unity to ensure system's stability, and the average packet service time is computed as $E(X) = \frac{1}{\mu} = \frac{8\bar{L}}{C}$, where \bar{L} is the average packet length (in bytes) and C is the server's bit rate (in bps). In the M/M/1 queuing model, there is also an exact formula for obtaining delay percentiles D_q , as:

$$D_q = E(X) \frac{1}{1-\rho} \ln \frac{1}{1-q} \quad (2)$$

However, in real network traffic, service times are not exponentially distributed. Instead, they follow some generic packet size distribution with multiple typical packet lengths.

For instance, the Amsterdam Internet Exchange Point (AMS-IX) shows a packet size distribution with a mean of $\bar{L} = 1019.03$ bytes and a standard deviation of $\sigma_L = 1161.66$ bytes (thus the squared coefficient of variation $C_L^2 = \frac{\sigma_L^2}{\bar{L}^2} = 1.30$) [14]. The San Francisco SFM-IX shows a mean of 1750.41 bytes and a standard deviation of 2062.69 bytes (thus a squared coefficient of variation of 1.39) [15]. These distributions capture the diversity of real packet sizes encountered on the Internet.

It is worth remarking that the coefficient of variation of a random variable X is defined as the ratio between its standard deviation and mean:

$$C_X^2 = \frac{Var(X)}{[E(X)]^2} \quad (3)$$

and has a critical impact on queuing delays and their variability.

As stated in [13], [16], [17], M/G/1 queuing models can be used at sub-millisecond time scales in modern high-capacity links, as long as sufficient uncorrelated traffic flows are aggregated together. Unfortunately, there is no closed-form solution for the CDF of latency like in the M/M/1 case; only the Pollaczek-Khinchine formula for the average waiting time in queue W_q is often used by the network community:

$$E(W_q)_{M/G/1} = E(X) \frac{\rho}{1-\rho} \frac{1+C_X^2}{2} \quad (4)$$

but does not provide a simple equation for the CDF or ways to obtain theoretical equations for delay percentiles.

Thus, the goal of this article is to find the closest M/M/1 queuing model (we call it queuing envelope) that acts as an upper bound for real M/G/1 queues with empirically-observed packet size distributions, like those from AMS-IXP and SFM-IXP. To do this, we define Algorithm 1 which seeks the smallest value of ρ_{env} or $\rho_{M/M/1}$ that acts as an upper bound for a real M/G/1 queue whose load is ρ_{real} or $\rho_{M/G/1}$. In other words, we aim to approximate an M/G/1 queue fed with real network traffic by the closest M/M/1 queuing model whose delay is always above the real one for percentiles above the median (50%), therefore acting as an upper bound of real delay:

Find $\min(\rho_{env})$ such that $D_{env} \geq D_{real}$

for delay percentiles above 50%

Here, D_{real} refers to the real delay observed in an M/G/1 queue fed with real network traffic, and D_{env} refers to the closest upper bound M/M/1 envelope delay found by Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Envelope M/M/1 Load Calculation

- 1: **Input:**
 - 2: *mg1_packets*: simulated packet delays from M/G/1 system
 - 3: E_X : average service time for M/G/1 system
 - 4: E_{T_real} : average delay for M/G/1 system
 - 5: **Initialize** *percentiles_seq* \leftarrow seq(0.5, 0.99, 0.01) ▷
from 50% to 99%
 - 6: **Calculate** *df_real*: Real M/G/1 quantiles from 50% to 99% for *mg1_packets*
 - 7: **Initialize** $\rho_{env} \leftarrow$ seq(from=0.01, to=0.99, by=0.01) ▷
Candidate M/M/1 loads: from 0.01 to 0.99 with step 0.01
 - 8: **for** each ρ in ρ_{env} **do**
 - 9: **Calculate** *df_env* \leftarrow $qexp(percentiles_seq, \lambda_{rate} = \frac{1-\rho}{E_X})$ M/M/1 envelope quantiles from 50% to 99%
 - 10: **if** all(*df_real* < *df_env*) **then**
 - 11: **Return** ρ and $\frac{E_X}{1-\rho}$
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: **Output:** Envelope M/M/1 load (ρ_{env}) and its average delay
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Fig. 1 (a) illustrates an example of the applicability of Algorithm 1. In the figure, the blue histogram is obtained from delays of an M/G/1 queue fed with real traffic following the SFM-IXP packet size distribution; in green, the M/M/1 queuing envelope, that is, an exponential distribution with mean $E(D_{env}) = E(X) \frac{1}{1-\rho_{env}}$. The Quantile function is also depicted in Fig. 1 (b) where, as shown, the M/M/1 envelope model is always above the real one for percentiles above the median, acting as a tight upper delay bound. The scenario considers a queue fed with real SFM-IXP traffic (packet size distribution) operating at 10 Gbit/s and real load $\rho_{real} = 0.7$.

Fig. 1: PDF of delay simulated packets (a) their percentiles (b) in one hop for M/G/1 SFMIX and M/M/1 envelope

Algorithm 1 finds that the smallest envelope load for using an M/M/1 as the upper bound is $\rho_{env} = 0.78$. The average (real) delay is:

$$E(D_{real}) = 5.34 \mu s$$

while the average delay according to the envelope follows:

$$E(D_{env}) = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - \rho_{env}} = 6.36 \mu s$$

The M/M/1 envelope also provides an exact formula (see eq. 2) for computing delay percentiles:

$$D_{0.90,env} = 1.40 \mu s \frac{1}{1 - 0.78} \ln \frac{1}{1 - 0.90} = 14.65 \mu s$$

$$D_{0.99,env} = 1.40 \mu s \frac{1}{1 - 0.78} \ln \frac{1}{1 - 0.99} = 29.31 \mu s$$

while the real quantile values, according to the histogram of Fig. 1 are $12.44 \mu s$ and $24.77 \mu s$, thus acting as slightly higher upper bounds.

III. SIMULATIONS AND ML MODEL FITTING

To validate the M/M/1 envelope calculation defined in Algorithm 1, we use `simmer` [18], a discrete-event simulator (DES) implemented in R, very useful to model queuing networks.

Our methodology was applied to different packet size distributions commonly observed in real-world network environments, namely:

- 1) **Trimodal** A tri-modal distribution with packet sizes of 40 Bytes, 576 Bytes, and 1500 Bytes, with weighted probabilities of $\frac{7}{12}$, $\frac{4}{12}$, and $\frac{1}{12}$, respectively, found in [18]. This distribution has an average packet size of 340.33 bytes, a standard deviation of 428.01 bytes, and a coefficient of variation of $C_X^2 = 1.58$, capturing a mix of small, medium, and large packet sizes typically observed in network traffic.
- 2) **Amsterdam** A distribution based on traffic data from the AMS-IXP Amsterdam Internet Exchange, which has an average packet size of 1019.03 Bytes, a standard deviation of 1161.66 Bytes, and a coefficient of variation of $C_X^2 = 1.30$ ¹. This distribution represents a large-scale Internet exchange point, capturing the diversity of packet sizes encountered in a major interconnection point.
- 3) **San Francisco** A distribution based on traffic data from the SFM-IXP San Francisco Metropolitan Internet Exchange, with parameters of 1750.41 Bytes for the average packet size, a standard deviation of 2062.69 Bytes, and $C_X^2 = 1.39$ for the coefficient of variation². This distribution represents a regional Internet exchange point, potentially exhibiting different characteristics than the global AMS-IX.

By considering these three diverse service time distributions, the study aims to evaluate the accuracy and applicability of the M/M/1 envelope approximation across a range of traffic scenarios, from synthetic tri-modal distributions to real-world traffic patterns observed at different Internet exchange points. This approach allows for a comprehensive assessment of the approximation's performance and its suitability for modeling queuing delays in DetNet environments with varying packet size distributions and traffic characteristics.

Fig. 2 illustrates the relationship between the load of the M/M/1 envelope and the load of the M/G/1 models for different packet size distributions, along with fitted second-order polynomial approximations.

The equations for the fitted polynomials in Fig. 2 are:

- Tri-modal: $\rho_{env} = 0.49 + 0.13 \cdot \rho_{real} + 0.39 \cdot \rho_{real}^2$
- AMS-IX: $\rho_{env} = 0.43 + 0.13 \cdot \rho_{real} + 0.47 \cdot \rho_{real}^2$
- SFM-IX: $\rho_{env} = 0.50 + 0.16 \cdot \rho_{real} + 0.34 \cdot \rho_{real}^2$

The worst-case scenario shown in Fig. 2 corresponds to the SFM-IX size distribution, which can be taken as a reference for the next section's numerical examples.

¹AMS-IX Amsterdam Internet Exchange, <https://stats.ams-ix.net/sflow/size.html>

²SFMIX San Francisco Metropolitan Internet Exchange, <https://sfmix.org/>

Fig. 2: Relationship between M/G/1 real load and M/M/1 envelope bound

Finally, it is worth noticing from the figures that as the system's load increases, the queuing delay distribution in the M/G/1 system gradually converges towards an exponential distribution with the mean of eq. 4, as stated by the Kingman's law of congestion [19]. This behavior is expected, as the M/M/1 queuing model, which assumes exponentially distributed service times, becomes a closer approximation to the M/G/1 system under high load conditions [20].

Consequently, the delay characteristics of both real and envelope models become increasingly similar as the system approaches saturation (i.e., when $\rho \rightarrow 1$). This convergence suggests that the M/M/1 envelope provides a tighter upper bound approximation for the delays in the M/G/1 system under higher load conditions.

The convergence of the delay distributions and the envelope load towards the M/G/1 model can be attributed to the fact that as the system becomes heavily loaded, the impact of the service time distribution diminishes, and the queuing dynamics become dominated by the arrival process. In such scenarios, the exponential assumption of the M/M/1 model becomes a reasonable approximation, and the envelope provides a conservative estimate of the worst-case delays experienced in the more general M/G/1 system.

IV. USING THE ENVELOPE MODEL FOR FINDING DELAY BOUNDS

As a **numerical example 1**, let us consider a scenario where a single node (for instance, a Access Central Office) collects the traffic packets of $H = 3,000$ households, and forwards the aggregated stream toward the Metropolitan Area Network (MAN) using a 10 Gb/s fiber link, in line with the scenarios defined in [21].

The average traffic per user is approximately $a = 1 \text{ Mb/s}$ with a standard deviation of $\sigma_a = 0.8 \text{ Mb/s}$, in line with forecasted estimates for residential traffic of [22]. We are interested in estimating the 90-th delay percentile of latency perceived by a packet chosen at random in the upstream link from the Access Node into the MAN, at 10 Gb/s.

Following the central limit theorem, we can assume that the aggregated traffic is normally distributed $N(H \cdot a, H \cdot \sigma_a^2)$, that is, with a mean of 3 Gb/s and standard deviation of 0.044 Gb/s. Our rule of dimensioning would be to consider as peak traffic $A_{\text{peak}} = 3 + 3 \cdot 0.044 = 3.13 \text{ Gb/s}$. Thus, the real average system's load is:

$$\rho_{\text{real}} = \frac{3.13 \text{ Gb/s}}{10 \text{ Gb/s}} = 0.313$$

or 31.3%.

The next step is to make use of the M/M/1 envelope model. To do so, first we need to find the model's load for the upper-bound using the polynomial regression curve:

$$\rho_{\text{env}} = 0.50 + 0.16 \cdot 0.313 + 0.34 \cdot 0.313^2 = 0.583$$

Although the real load is 31.3%, the M/M/1 envelope model's load rises to 58.3%. Thus, the real delay experienced by the packets in the upstream link is upper bounded by an M/M/1 model with such envelope load $\rho_{\text{env}} = 58.3\%$.

With this, we can now use the M/M/1 equations reviewed in section II to easily compute:

- The average delay:

$$E(D_{\text{env}}) = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - \rho_{\text{env}}} = 1.4 \mu\text{s} \frac{1}{1 - 0.583} = 3.35 \mu\text{s}$$

where $E(X) = \mu^{-1} = 1.4 \mu\text{s}$ for the average SFM-IX packet transmitted at 10 Gb/s.

- The 90-th delay percentile as:

$$D_{0.90, \text{env}} = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - \rho_{\text{env}}} \ln \frac{1}{1 - 0.9} = 7.71 \mu\text{s}$$

- The 99-th delay percentile as:

$$D_{0.99, \text{env}} = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - \rho_{\text{env}}} \ln \frac{1}{1 - 0.99} = 15.43 \mu\text{s}$$

The **numerical example 2** illustrates the accuracy of the M/M/1 envelope approximation for a different network scenario. In this scenario, we have a packet-optical node with coherent pluggable transceivers operating at 400 Gb/s and AMS-IX traffic distribution.

The goal is to compare the simulated packet delays obtained from simulation with the delays computed using the M/M/1 envelop upper bound model. This comparison is performed by evaluating the average delays, as well as the 99th percentile of the delay distributions, against the corresponding quantiles of the simulated data.

Fig. 3 shows both real and M/M/1 envelope upper bound values for the average delay, 90-th and 99-th percentiles of packet delays in scenarios at different link loads at 400 Gb/s.

The results demonstrate that the simulated delays are consistently below the corresponding upper bound values computed using the M/M/1 envelope model. This validates that the proposed M/M/1 envelope serves as a tight upper bound for the queuing delays. In this case, the difference between the real delay and the value obtained with the envelope upper bound is below $0.5 \mu\text{s}$ for the average delay, and below $1 \mu\text{s}$ for high delay percentiles like 90-th and 99-th.

Fig. 3: Comparison of theoretical M/M/1 envelope and simulated M/G/1 delays for AMS-IX traffic distribution

V. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

Evaluating network latency bounds is critical for network operators willing to ensure QoS to users and industries using real-time network applications like AR/VR, telemedicine and autonomous driving, with tight delay requirements.

This article has proposed a methodology for finding accurate models that enable fast calculation of delay percentiles. The model uses empirically observed packet traces and feeds this to a discrete-event simulator, estimates the latency CDF at different network conditions (namely load) and finds a simple closed-form model (based on well-known M/M/1 queuing theory).

This model, called the envelope model, allows to theoretically calculate delay percentiles which are above the real ones (upper bound). This allows for dimensioning and planning networks where latency guarantees are required, like in DetNet scenarios.

The algorithm for finding M/M/1 envelopes and code for re-running this work's simulations can be found open-source in Github [23].

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